

Methodology for defining homogeneous water bodies for management purposes

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Homogeneous water masses
Toxic algae management
Estuarine management
Transitional waters
Limfjorden

ABSTRACT

European legislation requires monitoring of toxic algae in marine areas where shellfish are harvested for consumption. Monitoring assumes the existence of homogeneous water bodies, the definition of which have important implications for stakeholders and consumers. Yet, the definition of homogeneous water bodies remains unclear. Here we present a methodology to divide coastal and estuarine waters into homogeneous water bodies to monitor toxic algae. The proposed method is mainly based on water transport, and secondarily on oceanographic characteristics; salinity and sea surface height. We apply the methodology to the Limfjord in Denmark and demonstrate its usefulness in areas with a complicated coastal morphology. The oceanographic descriptors applied in the method are standard outputs from coastal hydrodynamical models. Provided that validated and high resolution model output is available for a given area, the technique is thus adaptable to other morphologically and oceanographically complicated estuarine and coastal areas where toxic algae monitoring is necessary.

1. Introduction

Blooms of toxin-producing algae are a recurring phenomenon in Northern European estuarine and coastal waters, including the inner Danish waters and the eastern North Sea (Karlson et al., 2021). Due to bio-accumulation in filter-feeders and fish, toxic algae are a significant concern for fisheries and aquaculture industries (Berdalet et al., 2016) as they are transmitted up the food chain, with the risk of causing severe shellfish poisoning in humans (Jørgensen and Andersen, 2007; Tangen, 1983; Ayres, 1975). Bio-accumulation in shellfish can potentially occur even when toxic algae only exist in moderate concentrations (Reguera et al., 2016). To secure food safety, monitoring for toxic algae must be conducted regularly in all marine areas where shellfish are harvested (European Community, 2019). Thus, for management, including hygienic monitoring of bacteria, European legislation requires shellfish harvesting areas to be divided into management units for algae monitoring (Serret et al., 2020; European Community, 2019), hereafter named “algae monitoring areas” (AMAs), and “production areas” (PAs) for hygienic monitoring. AMA's are defined as water bodies assumed to be spatially uniform, a homogeneous water mass. When a water sample

from a given AMA tests positive for algae toxicity, all mussel harvesting in this same AMA will be temporarily closed to ensure food safety. PA's are operational areas based on needs for managing water quality. There are no requirements demanding AMA's and PA's to overlap, and often is an AMA a composite of multiple PA's.

The term “homogeneous water mass” is commonly used with regards to water management, e.g. in the US Clean Water Act from 1972 and the European Water Framework Directive (WFD, European Community, 2000). However, neither of these, nor the European Community (2019), give a clear definition of such a water mass, leaving the final definition to the individual state (European Community, 2004b), preferably based on local oceanographic conditions (Reguera et al., 2016).

Defining a homogeneous water mass is non-trivial. Especially, estuaries and coastal zones are characterized by large variability in space and time, making it challenging to assess the spread of a toxic algae bloom, which depends on a number of factors, such as the morphology of the area where the bloom initially occurs, wind conditions, general water movements as well as the degradation rate of the toxin (Reguera et al., 2016). Thus, it is necessary to develop an overall management-focused framework for homogeneous water-body definition while

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adapting to local conditions and needs (Serret et al., 2020). Traditionally, the classification of coastal and estuarine water masses has been based on salinity (Pritchard, 1967) following the Venice declaration (Venice System, 1958), with further developments including stratification (Jay and Smith, 1988), the effect of tides at the mouth of estuaries and rivers (Meire and Vincx, 1993), as well as combinations of the salinity, stratification and tidal flow (Prandle, 1985) and circulation combined with stratification (Oey, 1984). For management purposes, a division into natural boundaries, such as a narrowing between two basins, is practical and simple (e.g. Brenner et al., 2006; Wazniak et al., 2004), while more recent definitions employ more complicated methods, combining physical parameters as above (Da Silva and Rodrigues, 2004), as well as physical and biological factors (Ferreira et al., 2006).

The Limfjord is a shallow and biologically productive strait connecting the North Sea in the west to the Kattegat in the east. The fjord plays an important role for the local economy through, e.g. transport, fishing, mussel farming, and recreational activities, such as swimming and boating (Wiethüchter, 2008). Bivalve fisheries are the most important type of fishery in the Limfjord (Maar et al., 2021), making toxic algae blooms in the fjord, which occur on a yearly basis, a pertinent concern (Karlson et al., 2021; Kremp et al., 2019).

Following European legislation (European Community, 2019), Danish waters are at present divided into AMAs for toxic algae monitoring. For the majority of Danish waters, this division is based on an advective time scale derived from ocean current velocities of the 3D HBM (Hiromb-BOOS) Baltic Sea ocean model (Jakobsen and Mohn, 2017; She et al., 2007). The AMAs of the Limfjord are, however, currently based on the recommendations of local stakeholders. While this division of the Limfjord is economically viable and practical for management, it lacks verifiable scientific grounds and thus needs to be updated.

One option to divide the Limfjord into AMAs is to use the existing monitoring regarding physical and biological parameters, following Christiansen (2005) and BERNET CATCH (2006). However, the sampling of relevant indicators with sufficient temporal and spatial frequency would be logistically and financially challenging. At the same time, a limited dataset in space and/or time makes the division uncertain. Another option is to base the homogeneous water masses on hydrodynamical model results (e.g. Jakobsen and Mohn, 2017), as suggested by Serret et al. (2020). However, traditional hydrodynamical models are challenged by the complicated morphology of the inner Danish waters. The Limfjord is in particular, with several islands, side fjords and narrow sounds, difficult to describe using standard uniformly structured model grids. On the other hand, unstructured models can adapt to the morphology, thereby making them an obvious choice for hydrodynamical modeling of such areas. FlexSem is a finite difference - finite volume coastal hydrodynamical model running on an unstructured grid (Larsen et al., 2020), which has shown promising results in the Limfjord (Pastor et al., 2021; Maar et al., 2021), thus providing a good foundation for defining the homogeneous water masses in complicated waters such as the Limfjord.

Here, we present a semi-quantitative methodology to characterize AMAs for use in monitoring toxic algae based on the hydrodynamical FlexSem model. This methodology aims at coastal and estuarine waters with a complicated morphology, such as the inner Danish waters, and is applied to the Limfjord in northern Denmark. We demonstrate that the methodology is reliable, and sufficiently simple to be operationally feasible and broadly applicable. However, the large variability in coastal and estuarine waters, combined with necessary local considerations, makes it impossible to create a purely deterministic method for homogeneous water body definitions. Instead, we use several descriptors to indicate physically meaningful boundaries of management areas.

2. Methodology and case study

2.1. Description of the fjord system

The Limfjord is a shallow fjord system, located in northern Denmark, connecting the North Sea in the west with the Kattegat in the east (Fig. 1). The westerly winds cause episodically sea level changes at the western boundary of the fjord, generating inflows of high saline water into the fjord from the North Sea and are the main drivers of the general eastward water movement along the fjord (Larsen et al., 2017a). At times of large inflows, the water level is increased in the western part of the fjord, in some instances causing localized storm surges due to the accumulation of water in areas of restricted flow (Knudsen et al., 2012). During periods of weaker winds, a backflow towards the North Sea in the west occurs (Riisgård and Goldstein, 2014). The average tidal range is 0.4 to 0.5 m at the western end of the fjord. By the eastern border of the fjord, the maximum sea surface height from tides is 0.2 to 0.3 m. The tidal range in the middle of the fjord is small (Larsen et al., 2017a). While the wind systems generally control the water inflow to the fjord, the tidal motion can be the main force of water movements in the fjord in times of weak winds (Larsen et al., 2017b).

The salinity in the fjord is controlled by the semi-equilibrium between the inflow of salty water from the North Sea, of low-salinity water from the Kattegat and the supply of freshwater from local point sources, especially from the Skive-Lovns sub-estuary (Fig. 2). The salinity by the western boundary is 32 to 34 psu while it is approximately 19 to 25 at the eastern boundary, creating a salinity gradient along the fjord.

2.2. Hydrodynamical simulation

We based the first step in the AMA definition (Fig. 4) on a hydrodynamical simulation of the Limfjord carried out by the coastal model FlexSem. FlexSem is a 3D hydrodynamical model, which solves the standard Navier-Stokes equations using a finite difference, finite volume discretization (Larsen et al., 2020). FlexSem runs on an unstructured mesh, making it ideal for the simulations of the inner Danish waters, which are characterized by a complicated coast line and water flow. The model is fast to set up and run for new domains, and has so far been used in studies of e.g. the Limfjord (Pastor et al. (2021)), Horsens Fjord, the Pacific Ocean and Zanzibar (Larsen et al., 2020).

In the current setup of the Limfjord, the horizontal resolution ranged from 300 m to approximately 1 km (Fig. 2). In the vertical, the resolution was 1 m. The average depth in the domain was 6.6 m, and the maximum 30 m. Initial fields and boundary conditions for salinity, temperature, horizontal velocities and sea surface height, as well as atmospheric forcing, were supplied by the Hiromb-BOOS Model (HBM, Murawski et al., 2021). Runoff from land (Fig. 2) was provided by the SWAT catchment model (Molina-Navarro et al., 2017), with daily resolution. The current FlexSem setup is a further development from setup used by Pastor et al. (2021), with changes including improved turbulence scheme, run-off data, boundary conditions and forcing. The new setup performs well when assessed against available data (Appendix A).

For our study, the model was run for the years 2009 to 2017, which are also the years we are using to identify AMAs in the Limfjord.

2.3. Seasonal focus

Toxic algae occurrences have mainly been detected from April to October in the Limfjord (Kremp et al., 2019), while mussel harvesting takes place from March to December, with breaks during summer due to e.g. oxygen deficiency and during winter due to ice cover (Larsen et al., 2017b). Due to the distribution of toxic algae and mussel harvesting over the full year, we used annual averages of the model output when determining the distribution of the AMAs, following Jakobsen and Mohn (2017). The seasonal variations were taken into account by reviewing the temporal standard deviation of our indicators of choice as described

Fig. 1. Left) Overview of the Danish waters, located in the transition area between the North Sea and the Baltic Sea. The area of the Limfjord is marked by the black square. Right) Map of the Limfjord, with relevant water bodies named.

Fig. 2. Left: Map of the Limfjord model domain, including the unstructured grid of FlexSem. The background color marks the depth. The dots show the locations of the freshwater-sheds running into the fjord along with the magnitude of each fresh water source. Right: Zoom of the highly resolved area marked by a red square in the left subplot. Here the mesh is plotted in white. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Map of the Limfjord overlaid with polygons of the production areas (PAs), marked with the identification numbers used for water management (European Community, 2004a). The production areas are used as minimum areas for the homogeneous water mass definition in this study.

below.

2.4. Minimum management areas

Given the high intrinsic variability of estuaries and the coastal zone, which is well resolved by the FlexSem model, we follow Hansen et al. (2021) and Ferreira et al. (2006) and introduced the concept of minimum management areas to avoid proliferation of the number of management units (Fig. 4). In the current study, we used the production areas in the Limfjord (PAs, Fig. 3) as minimum areas for a homogeneous water mass. The PAs were defined for the sanitary survey following (European Community, 2004a), and thus connected to the AMAs, the definition of which is the purpose of the current study. In comparison, the grid polygons of the Atlantis model were used as minimum management areas in the Barents Sea (Hansen et al., 2021), while coastal morphology and bathymetry was proposed as boundaries for these areas in Portuguese estuaries (Ferreira et al., 2006).

2.5. Methodology for water body division

In the current study, we used oceanographic characteristics as system descriptors (e.g. Table 1) to define AMAs. This follows the suggestions of Reguera et al. (2016) and the European Water Framework Directive, system B (e.g. Henocque and Andral, 2003).

We used a two-step approach to define the homogeneous water bodies before harmonizing these pre-AMAs into the final AMAs (Fig. 4).

1. Flux-based characterization (Section 2.5.1): The annual mean vertically integrated water transport, and hence transport of toxic algae, was considered the primary indicator of the connectivity between the PAs. The transport was calculated across key sections based on the location of PAs in combination with the morphology of the water body in question.
2. State-based characterization (Section 2.5.2): Subsequently, a number of natural characteristics were used to determine whether a further division was prudent. In the current study, the descriptors used were sea surface height (SSH) and surface salinity. This step can be modified to include other appropriate descriptors (e.g. Table 1), depending on the nature of the water body.

2.5.1. Flux-based characterization

The morphology of a given area affects ocean currents by e.g. restricting or facilitating the water flow, and introducing mixing. It thus has implications for other factors such as salinity, SSH, and distribution of water-borne particles, such as toxic algae. Morphology is thus a key component to take into account when defining a homogeneous water mass (Bartley et al., 2001). In the current study, we calculated the water transport across the sections making up boundaries between the PAs (Fig. 3). In most cases, the location of the PAs provided a good basis for

Table 1

Examples of natural characteristics used to define homogeneous water masses for management purposes.

Descriptor	Previously applied in e.g.
Coastal morphology	Spain & Mexico (Brenner et al., 2006; Bartley et al., 2001)
Salinity	Denmark & Portugal (Christiansen, 2005; Ferreira et al., 2006)
Tidal range	Denmark & Portugal (Christiansen, 2005; Ferreira et al., 2006)
Stratification	Denmark and Spain (Christiansen, 2005; Borja et al., 2006)
Fresh water flow	Portugal (Da Silva and Rodrigues, 2004)
Current velocity	Denmark & general (Jakobsen and Mohn, 2017; Prandle, 1985)
Depth	France (Henocque and Andral, 2003)
Residence time	Denmark & Europe (Carstensen et al., 2005; Tett et al., 2003)

Fig. 4. Schematic overview of the methodology used to divide estuarine and coastal waters.

water transport calculations. However, given the complicated coastline of the Limfjord, the sections did in some instances have to be aggregated or modified according to morphology, e.g. to avoid a section ending mid-water. This resulted in a total of 33 sections in the Limfjord (Fig. 5).

After defining the location of sections, we calculated the net water transport and the temporal standard deviation (STD) of the net water transport. While the net transport can mask a significant oscillating flow, the STD takes the time variability into account. Therefore, the STD is vital in areas where the flow alternates between a net in- and outflow, such as the western Limfjord.

The water bodies were subsequently defined based on the following:

- The direction and strength of net water transport. In morphologically complicated water bodies, the direction of the net water transport can give a first indication of the system's connectivity.
- To further group production areas into homogeneous water bodies based on the STD of the water transport, we used a similarity index (SI) following Ferreira et al. (2006):

$$SI_{i,i+1} = \frac{|STD_i - STD_{i+1}|}{0.5(STD_{i-1} + STD_{i+1})} \quad (1)$$

Here, $SI_{i, i+1}$ is the similarity index between neighboring section i and $i + 1$, and STD denotes the STD of the water transport over time. The SI tends towards zero when the transport is similar across the two sections, while a larger value of SI indicates a large difference in transport. The PAs were grouped into one AMA when $SI_{i, i+1} < SI_0$. We defined the cut-off value, SI_0 , as follows:

$$SI_0 = \overline{SI} + \sigma_{SI} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5. Left column) Orange line marks net water transport through four channels in the Limfjord, calculated at the boundaries between the PAs (Fig. 3). Negative values denote a south- or westerly direction. The shaded orange areas show the STD of the water transport over time. The background color mark the location of the corresponding PA in the map inserts in the right column. Notice that transports are calculated across the boundary between neighboring PAs, and thus refers to the transport from the PA to left on the x-axis, relative to the neighboring PA located to the right on the x-axis. For each channel, the cut-off value SI_0 (Eq. (2)) is written, and the PAs where $SI > SI_0$ is marked with an asterisk (*). Please refer to Fig. 3 for the PA numbers. Right column) Map of the Limfjord, the locations of the PAs through which transport is calculated in the left column. a and b) From the North Sea to the Kattegat, through western Løgstør Broad. c and d) Venø Bay. e and f) Thisted Channel. g and h) Skive to the Kattegat, through eastern Løgstør Broad, east of Livø. (See Fig. 1 for area names.) (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

\bar{SI} denotes the mean of the SI s along the transect of sections, and σ_{SI} is the STD of SI s. This approach meant that SI_0 varies with the degree of variability along the water body in question, keeps SI_0 consistent, and eliminated the need for human bias in choosing the cut-off value.

2.5.2. State-based characterization

For the state-based characterization it is necessary to choose appropriate descriptors of the system. In the current study, we used surface salinity and SSH as state descriptors. For simplicity, we

considered surface salinity, as the Limfjord, with an average depth of 5 m is a shallow system, where frequent wind mixing creates a strong benthic-pelagic coupling (Josefson and Rasmussen, 2000). As our homogeneous water body division was based on hydrodynamical model simulations, it was an advantage that both salinity and SSH are key parameters of hydrodynamical models, making them generally well validated and easy to obtain (e.g. Murawski et al., 2021; Gustafsson, 2012).

The mean and relative STD (STD normalized by the mean) of the

modeled SSH and surface salinity were calculated for each surface point in the model grid. The relative STD was used due to the gradients in surface salinity and SSH along the fjord. In cases with very low means it may be prudent to use the STD alone. Subsequently, these values were averaged in the horizontal domain to give one value for each PA (Fig. 3). We defined a model cell as belonging to a given PA based on the location of the center of the cell. Prior to grouping PAs into larger areas based on salinity and SSH, the values of these were normalized as follows:

$$z_i = \frac{x_i - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)} \quad (3)$$

Here, x denotes the descriptor in question (i.e. mean or STD of salinity and SSH), and z is the normalized value of that same descriptor at PA # i . Normalization made it possible to evaluate the robustness of the classes irrespective of the individual magnitude of the descriptors.

Subsequently, the PAs were grouped into pre-AMAs, which were homogeneous with respect to the descriptor in question. The bins for grouping were determined to make the state-based water body division coherent and spatially meaningful. Here, we grouped the water bodies based on the minimum and maximum of a given descriptor:

$$\Delta z = \frac{z_{\max} - z_{\min}}{N} \quad (4)$$

N denotes the number of final water bodies. However, care is needed when choosing N ; a too high number will result in proliferation of homogeneous water bodies, whereas the number of final areas will tend towards one if N is too small.

2.5.3. Final water body division

From the flux- and state-based water body division, the final AMAs were created (Fig. 4). The flux-based definition was given the most weight, as the flux indicates the degree of algae transport between neighboring PAs, while the state-based definition acted to modify the pre-AMAs defined in the flux-based approach. When the borders were located in close proximity, a common border can be defined. In other instances, the different approaches will lead to different borders, making it necessary to judge whether to discard some borders or to create a larger number of final AMAs.

2.6. Defining AMAs in the Limfjord

2.6.1. Flux-based division

The net water transport through the Limfjord was calculated through the sections marked in Fig. 5 (right column). The transport was calculated across the borders between neighboring PAs. In most cases, the transport was calculated between single PAs. However, in Nissum Broad, it was calculated across the width of the channel, while some sections in Løgstør Broad were modified somewhat in order to avoid sections ending mid-basin. The resulting net water transport and the STD of the net transport is shown in Fig. 5, left column, for four channels in the fjord.

The first division of the fjord into AMAs was made based on the direction of the net water transport (solid orange line, Fig. 5). In the western channel, west of PA #13, the net transport was close to zero (Fig. 5a and c). In the Thisted channel, south of PA #32, the transport was small and south-westward (i.e. negative in Fig. 5e). In the Skive-Lovns area, eastern Løgstør Broad and in the eastern channel the transport was northwest-ward (Fig. 5g), while the western Løgstør Broad showed a more complicated flow pattern (Fig. 5a). The resulting division into four water bodies can be seen in Fig. 6a.

The high STDs of the water transport show that the Limfjord is subject to high variability in the flow, especially in the western channel (Fig. 5a). To further define the AMAs, we calculated the SI (Eq. (1)) from the STD, and applied a cut-off value SI_0 (Eq. (2)) to each of the four channels (Fig. 5). Locations where $SI > SI_0$, and thus make up a possible boundaries of the AMAs, are marked with an asterisk (*) in Fig. 5. The SI leads to the following pre-AMAs:

- The western channel of the Limfjord, from the North Sea to Løgstør Broad (Figs. 5a and 6b), was characterized by large variability in the strength and direction of the water transport, as demonstrated by the large STD of the net water transport (Fig. 5a). The SI of the STDs exceeded SI_0 in PA #15, at the entrance to Løgstør Broad, and again in PA #36 within Løgstør Broad.
- Venø Bay is a small side arm to the western channel, sheltered from the main flow by Venø Island. The bay was characterized by a relatively small mean flow, similar in magnitude to the mean flow in the western channel. However, there was a difference in STD of the net transport between Venø Bay and the western channel (Fig. 5c). This difference shows that the flow in Venø Bay is relatively constant and is affected by the large in- and outflow events to a much smaller degree. Consequently, we define Venø Bay as one pre-AMA (Fig. 6b).
- In Thisted channel, the STD of the water transport was relatively constant and low, with a clear boundary south of PA #23 (Fig. 5e). The large change in STD shows that the salt water inflows do not affect the channel to a large degree, and that the channel should be defined as one pre-AMA (Fig. 6b).

The large fresh water inflow to the Skive-Lovns sub-arm causes a net north-eastward flow, connecting Skive-Lovns to the eastern channel with a relatively slow but constant flow (Fig. 5d). This eastern part of the fjord is divided as follows:

- The net northward water flow from the Skive-Lovns area divided approximately evenly around the island of Livø. The area south of Livø does at times experience a reversed flow, as shown by the STD (Fig. 5g), with water coming from the western Løgstør Broad. The STD was reduced east of Livø, showing that the northward direction was constant here. The resulting difference in STD showed a possible boundary east of Livø.
- The eastern part of Løgstør Broad and the Eastern Channel of the fjord (Fig. 6b) was characterized by a net eastward flow. The

Fig. 6. a) Grouping of PAs into pre-AMAs based on net transport. b) Grouping of PAs into pre-AMAs based on the STD of net transport.

transport was strong relative to the remainder of the fjord, with a small STD, induced by transient inflows from the east.

2.6.2. State-based definition: sea surface height

When calculated over the reference level of the bathymetry, the mean SSH was lowest by the eastern border towards the Kattegat and highest in the Skive-Lovns fjord arm (Fig. 7a), where large volumes of freshwater enters the fjord (Fig. 2). Based on SSH and Eqs. (3) and (4), the fjord was divided into four water body classes. This resulted in four coherent and well-defined water bodies (Fig. 7b).

The most important factors affecting the STD of the SSH are the tidal currents occurring on an hourly time scale, inflow events from the North Sea to the western part of the fjord taking place on a time scale of weeks, and lastly the seasonal cycle of the freshwater inflow from local water sources. The STD was thus largest towards the western boundary, where the SSH is affected by tidal motions and inflow events, and became progressively smaller towards the Kattegat boundary in east (Fig. 7c). Based on the SSH STD and Eqs. (3) and (4), the fjord was divided into four pre-AMAs. The pre-AMAs are spatially coherent areas (Fig. 7d).

2.6.3. State-based definition: surface salinity

The surface salinity decreased from approximately 32 psu at the North Sea boundary in the west to 25 psu at the Kattegat boundary in the east, with the lowest concentrations in the fresh-water dominated Skive-Lovns fjord arm (Fig. 8a). Following the Venice declaration, we defined an euhaline salinity class with salinity >30 psu. Most of the PAs in the fjord, however, fell within the polyhaline salinity class ($18 \text{ psu} < \text{salinity} < 30 \text{ psu}$). We applied Eqs. (3) and (4) to divide the polyhaline type into three additional classes. The classes reflect the salinity gradient across the fjord, with the low-salinity classes in the east and in areas affected by a large freshwater supply and the high-salinity class towards the west (Fig. 8b).

Based on the STD of surface salinity, which was highest in the eastern channel and lowest in the Thisted channel, the fjord was divided into 4 pre-AMAs using Eqs. (3) and (4). This shows that the eastern channel, the Skive-Lovns area, the Thisted channel and Venø Bay have separate characteristics compared to the remainder of the fjord (Fig. 8d).

2.6.4. Final definition of water bodies

Based on flux- and state-based approaches we propose a total of eight AMAs (Fig. 9). Please refer to Fig. 1 for location names:

- The flux-based approach showed that the western channel is a well connected area with high variability (Fig. 5a). However, the state-based approach (Figs. 7 and 8) demonstrated that Nissum Broad has different characteristics with respect to salinity and SSH, compared to the remainder of the channel, likely due to a strong tidal influence. The Western Channel was thus divided into two AMAs: Nissum Broad and Kaas-Sallingsund (Fig. 9).
- Venø Bay: The island of Venø hinders a large flow of water into the bay, creating a semi-closed water mass here (Fig. 9).
- The Thisted channel (Fig. 9) is clearly defined through both the flux- and state-based approach (Figs. 6, 7 and 8).
- Western Løgstør Broad was characterized by strong gradient in the variability of the water transport and salinity. However, given the well-defined water masses surrounding this area combined with its relatively small extent, the Western Løgstør Broad is defined as one AMA (Fig. 6).
- Based on the water transport, the Skive-Lovns sub-arm is not well-defined (Fig. 6). However, the area is distinctly different from the remainder of the fjord when evaluated by the state-based approach, due large fresh water input from surrounding water-sheds. We place the final boundary between PA #16 and 17 (Fig. 9), as a compromise between the boundaries suggested by the flux- and the state-based approach (Figs. 6, 7 and 8).
- The eastern Løgstør Broad and Eastern channel. The channel is well connected to Løgstør Broad through the water flow. However, given the strong difference in salinity, SSH and the STD of the SSH, between the eastern channel and the eastern Løgstør Broad, we divide these into two AMAs (Fig. 9).

3. Discussion

3.1. Methodology

The methodology used in the current study builds on previous approaches to divide coastal and estuarine water bodies into homogeneous

Fig. 7. a) Modeled mean sea surface height calculated for each PA. b) Grouping of PAs into pre-AMAs based on SSH. c) Mean temporal SSH relative STD calculated for each PA. d) Grouping of PAs into pre-AMAs based on the STD of SSH.

Fig. 8. a) Mean modeled surface salinity calculated for each PA in the Limfjord. b) Grouping of PAs into pre-AMAs based on surface salinity. c) Mean seasonal surface salinity STD calculated for each PA. d) Grouping of PAs into pre-AMAs based on STD of surface salinity.

Fig. 9. Final AMAs based on the flux- and state-based approaches.

water bodies based on oceanographic characteristics and morphology (e.g. Jakobsen and Mohn, 2017; Ferreira et al., 2006; Brenner et al., 2006), and follows suggestions from the European Community to base the AMAs on hydrodynamical conditions (Serret et al., 2020). While the advective time scale-approach applied to the Danish waters outside of the Limfjord by Jakobsen and Mohn (2017) is not suitable for an unstructured model grid approach such as the one used in the current study (Fig. 2), we have built on their methodology by calculating the net transport across sections in the fjord, and used this transport to define the homogeneous water masses. Calculating the water transport across sections has the drawback of being un-suitable for larger open stretches of ocean. However, given the complicated morphology of the Limfjord, with associated complex flow patterns, calculating the transport across smaller sections is necessary to understand the water's movement. Another technique previously applied to Danish waters is to identify homogeneous water bodies by calculating the residence time of enclosed water bodies, such as fjords (Christiansen, 2005). The residence time for a given water body does, however, require a relatively well-defined water body, such as a whole fjord with a single entrance, while it is not realistic to calculate the residence time for smaller and more

complicated areas such as the Limfjord (Josefson and Rasmussen, 2000). The same applies to freshwater flow, as applied by Da Silva and Rodrigues (2004).

Evaluating the water transport with the flux-based approach gives a good understanding of the water's pathways, but can be ambiguous in terms of the location of boundaries between different water masses. Applying the state-based approach further adds understanding of the system at hand. Furthermore, oceanographic state descriptors have been used extensively to define water masses in previous studies (Table 1), and the approach thus ties to a long history of defining homogeneous water bodies. In Denmark, fjords have previously been divided into ten sub-types based on, e.g. salinity, stratification, water depth, and eelgrass depth distribution to implement the WFD (Christiansen, 2005; BERNET CATCH, 2006). In terms of salinity, most studies have relied on the Venice classification (Venice System, 1958) to divide water masses into salinity classes (Christiansen, 2005; Ferreira et al., 2006). This classification leads to the Limfjord having only two salinity classes, while (Christiansen, 2005) characterized all of the fjord as polyhaline (i.e. one zone), making it necessary to further divide the polyhaline class into sub-classes.

In the current study we use salinity and SSH as descriptors, as they both indicate the change from the marine zones at the boundaries of the fjord to the areas where fresh-water inflow controls the flow to a considerable degree. Another potential descriptor, which was tested for the Limfjord in the current study, is the strength of stratification. A stratified water column can potentially develop in the central basin of Løgstør Broad during calm conditions in summer, it affects the water transport through the fjord (Hofmeister et al., 2009), as well as the spread of toxic algae, by separating the bottom water from the surface water, thus reducing the volume in which the algae is distributed, while also separating mussel beds from the algae in the surface waters (Wiles et al., 2006). These studies assessed the potential energy anomaly (PEA). However, given the dependence of the PEA on the depth of the water, we found that the AMAs defined on basis of the PEA were more scattered due to local shallower PAs, as compared to the AMAs based on salinity and SSH, and the PEA was thus omitted as an indicator. This exercise showed that not all indicators are suitable for a given marine area, and that care must be taken when choosing an indicator.

An advantage of the methodology presented here is that it is based on relatively simple descriptors, which can be obtained from observations or hydrodynamical model simulations of a given area. While field observations traditionally have been used to define homogeneous water bodies (e.g. Ferreira et al., 2006), obtaining sufficient observations spatially and temporally remains a challenge. With increasing computational power, a rising number of hydrodynamical models with high horizontal resolution exist (e.g. Haid et al., 2020; Kuznetsov et al., 2020), providing the advantage of high resolution in time and space. However, before applying output from such models to define homogeneous water bodies as described, it is necessary to first evaluate the output of these models against available data and define possible shortcomings, as has been done in section Appendix A. Using descriptors that are readily available from a given hydrodynamic model suggests that our methodology is easily adaptable for other semi-enclosed estuarine or coastal waters, for which hydrodynamical model output exists. Further, the method is extendable to include other appropriate environmental descriptors of a given water body, such as tidal range, oxygen depletion and zooplankton grazing (Table 1). Furthermore, Serret et al. (2020) suggest that AMAs should be based on hydrodynamical models.

When applying the concept of minimum management areas following Hansen et al. (2021) and Ferreira et al. (2006), it is important to choose areas which are large enough to be realistic for management, while also making them sufficiently small to capture variability across the fjord. For the current study, the fact that each final AMA is made up of multiple PAs (Fig. 9) is an indication that the PAs are sufficiently small for the fjord. In the current study, the minimum management areas were defined as PAs (Fig. 3), a definition which can also be applied in other European waters where PAs are defined. However, it is also possible to choose a different definition, such as morphology of the fjord following Ferreira et al. (2006).

3.2. AMAs in the Limfjord

The final AMAs are important for mussel fisheries, as their layout controls the extend of possible temporary closure of mussel harvesting areas for food safety reasons (European Community, 2019) and at the same time ensure that harvested mussels can be used for consumption without risk of algae toxins. Even when a hydrodynamical simulation captures the variability of the fjord, it is, however, non-trivial to define boundaries of the homogeneous water masses (AMAs), given the continuous spatial and temporal changes in oceanographic properties (e.g. Serret et al., 2020). In the western channel, the episodic inflow events episodically reach as far as Løgstør Broad, as illustrated by the STD of the net flow (Fig. 5a). However, the euhaline salinity class only reaches Venø Bay (Fig. 8b) and the STD of the SSH has a large gradient between Nissum Broad and Løgstør Broad, showing that Nissum Broad and Venø Bay are affected by inflow from the North Sea (i.e. tidal motion and

inflow events) to a larger degree than the remainder of the Western Channel. Consequently, we define Nissum Broad as a single AMA (Fig. 9).

The spread of the water from the North Sea is especially important to monitor, as it has the potential to bring algae toxicity into the fjord (Wietkamp et al., 2020) where it can potentially reach the mussel harvesting grounds in the Kaas-Sallingsund final AMA (Larsen et al., 2017a). The boundaries between the main inflow channel (Nissum Broad and the western channel, Fig. 9) and neighboring AMAs (Venø Bay and Thisted channel, Fig. 9) are well-defined based on the STD of North Sea water inflow (Fig. 5a, b and c), as the similarity index (SI Eq. (1)) is sufficiently large for the boundary location to be robust with a wide range of cut-off values (SI_0 , Eq. (2)), indicating that the degree of mixing between these AMAs is relatively small. The salinity and the variability of salinity likewise show large gradients between the western channel and the Thisted channel (Fig. 8b and d), with the two southernmost PAs ending in different pre-AMAs compared to the remainder of Thisted Channel. This firstly illustrates that some mixing does take place between the two AMAs, and secondly it shows that the state-based approach is an indication of differences between water masses, and should not in all cases dictate boundaries between AMAs. In Thisted channel, mussel harvesting areas are located north of PA 23 and 24 (Fig. 3), which are classified as a marine protected area (Larsen et al., 2018). The Intermittent northward-flowing water in the southern part of the channel is thus of less concern regarding food safety. The mussel harvesting grounds in the north of the channel are mainly affected by water coming from the north.

The water dynamics in Løgstør Broad is more complicated, less well defined and thus difficult to quantify. The water movements are affected by occasional inflow from the North Sea, the Kattegat and from the freshwater dominated Skive-Lovns fjord arm, while also being topographically affected by the islands in the area. The main divider in Løgstør Broad is the east-west division created by the water flow from Skive-Lovns to the Kattegat (Fig. 6), while the state-based approach is difficult to apply here due to the small gradients in salinity and SSH (Figs. 7 and 8). Additionally, the boundary between the Western Channel and Løgstør Broad is challenging to define using the flux-based approach as small changes to the SI_0 would result in different boundaries. In this case, having a clear definition for SI_0 (Eq. (2)) is an advantage. Further, the boundary is consistent between the flux-based approach and the two descriptors in the state-based approach, adding to our confidence that the boundary is located in the optimal location (Figs. 7 and 8).

While the eastern Løgstør Broad is characterized by a relatively constant current going from the Skive-Lovns sub-estuary to the Kattegat, the Skive-Lovns fjord arm shows up as a rather distinct area in the state-based approach with low salinity and high SSH (Figs. 7 and 8). The final boundary between the Skive-Lovns and the eastern Løgstør Broad AMAs (Fig. 9) are a compromise between the boundaries found through the flux- and the state-based approaches (Figs. 6, 8 and 7). Toxic algae have repeatedly been observed in the Skive-Lovns fjord-arm, possibly due to resting cysts in the sediment (Kremp et al., 2019). Mussel fisheries have historically mainly been carried out in the Skive fjord-arm (PA 22, Fig. 3), and to a smaller degree in the remainder of the Skive-Lovns final AMA. Given the northward water transport in the area, it is prudent for the northern AMA border to be located further north than the main harvesting grounds.

The Eastern Channel (Fig. 9) is connected to Løgstør Broad through the north-eastward water transport (Fig. 6) coming mainly from the Skive-Lovns fjord-arm. However, in the state-based approach both surface salinity and SSH defines the Eastern Channel as a separate water mass. This division is consistent with the findings of Murawski et al. (2021), who showed that the fjord can be divided into two domains with regards to SSH; in the Eastern Channel the SSH is controlled by the signal from the Kattegat, while SSH in the rest of the fjord is controlled by the conditions in the North Sea. Consequently, we define the eastern

channel as a separate AMA. As no mussel harvesting grounds are located in the eastern channel (Feld et al., 2020), the transport of toxic algae into this area is of lesser concern.

The origin of intermittent toxic algae blooms in the Limfjord is not fully understood, though transport of algae from the North Sea, as well as benthic resting cysts, which have been observed in all areas of the inner fjord, act as possible seeds for a bloom (Karlson et al., 2021; Kremp et al., 2019). In compliance with European legislation (European Community, 2019), the presence of toxic algae is routinely monitored across the fjord through sampling. Our methodology for defining AMAs thus emphasizes transport of toxic algae to identify AMAs, and thereby point out the areas at risk when toxic algae have been identified in a given AMA. In general, a well connected system like the Limfjord should be monitored upstream of farms, and in the inflow areas of the AMAs, in the interest of early detection of algae toxicity (Reguera et al., 2016), as no water mass is completely separated from the surroundings. This is especially important in a shallow and seasonally warm system like the Limfjord, where toxic algae are not easily flushed from the system.

3.3. Variation with time

A given oceanographic characteristic, such as salinity or SSH, is subject to variations in both space and time. To include the seasonal changes, we take the temporal STD into account when defining homogeneous water bodies. This simplified approach is necessary in terms of analyzing the model output and obtaining straightforward answers, which are necessary for management purposes. This averaged approach is realistic for the majority of situations. However, it may have the effect that extreme events, such as storm surges or prolonged calm periods, are not well represented by the AMAs.

On a seasonal scale, the spring and summer months tend towards being more stable than the winter and autumn; solar heating and relatively low average wind strength lead to a less dynamic water column during summer, while stronger winds during winter leads to larger inflow events in the Limfjord and occasional storm surges. As algae blooms tend to occur in the warmer months, the extreme mixing during winter is less of a concern than a stagnant water column conducive for algae growth. In times of little flow, there is a risk of local blooms, which are not captured by monitoring, and which can quickly spread once the wind and water flow increases. This, however, is a risk irrespective of the method of defining AMAs.

4. Conclusions

Here, we have presented a methodology to divide estuarine and coastal water bodies into homogeneous water masses. The method is primarily based on water transport (flux-based approach) and secondarily on a number of oceanographic descriptors (state-based approach). The secondary descriptors can be changed, depending on the water body in question, making the methodology broadly applicable. This method is based on the unstructured model FlexSem, especially well suited for morphologically complicated water bodies, such as the inner Danish waters.

Appendix A. Model validation

The simulation was carried out for the years 2009 to 2017. For simplicity, we here focus on 2017 for validation, but provide statistics for all years. Data for validation of temperature and salinity was obtained from the Danish national database on aquatic monitoring data (ODA, <https://odafora.lle.au.dk>).

A.1. Temperature

We have demonstrated the applicability of the methodology by using it to define algae monitoring areas (AMAs) for toxic algae management in the Limfjord, Denmark. For the current study, salinity and sea surface height are applied as descriptors used in the state-based approach as they are appropriate for the Limfjord, which is characterized by large gradients in both. The analysis results in eight AMAs. The AMAs in the western part of the fjord are well-defined by the flux-based approach, while the state-based approach is important in determining water body boundaries in the inner parts of the fjord less affected by the inflow of North Sea water. Our methodology relies on standard model output; velocity, salinity and SSH. It is thus easily adaptable to other morphologically complicated estuarine and coastal areas for which an oceanographic model simulation is available.

Given the strong gradients and large variability of coastal and estuarine zones, dividing the area into homogeneous water bodies is a non-trivial task, although necessary for management purposes. The methodology presented here provides a scientific basis for this division. However, the resulting AMAs have a potentially large impact on food safety and socioeconomic interests, and the final division must be made by managers, considering the natural characteristics presented here. Yet, the final verdict also needs to account for political and administrative considerations into account, as well as stakeholder and consumer interest.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vibe Schourup-Kristensen: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Methodology, Validation, Software, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Marie Maar:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – review & editing. **Janus Larsen:** Methodology, Validation, Software, Data curation. **Christian Mohn:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing. **Jens Murawski:** Validation, Resources. **Jun She:** Validation, Resources. **Hans H. Jakobsen:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

VSK and HHJ were funded by the “Framework Agreement on the Provision of Research-based Policy Support” between the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries of Denmark and Aarhus University. VSK, MM and JL were funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 - Research and Innovation Framework Programme (FutureMARES project, Grant No. 869300 and FORCOAST project, Grant No. 870465). We would like to thank anonymous reviewers for helpful comments and suggestion that helped to further the manuscript.

Fig. A.10. Modeled mean sea surface temperature for 2017. The black dots mark the location of the CTD stations used to validate the model output along with station numbers: 1) Nissum Broad, 2) Kås Broad, 3) Sallingsund, 4) Løgstør Broad West, 5) Løgstør Broad East, 6) Nibe Broad, 7) Hals, 8) Bjørnsholm Bay, 9) Riisgårde Broad 10) Hvalpsund, 11) Skive, 12) Lovns, 13) Visby Broad, 14) Vilsund, 15) Thisted Broad.

The restricted inflow of water through the narrow boundaries of the fjord, combined with fjord's shallow depth, have the consequence that the sea surface temperature (SST) is largely controlled by surface heat-fluxes. The relatively small extent of the fjord further means that the SST does not vary much across the spatial model domain. Nevertheless, the Limfjord is characterized by a decreasing temperature gradient from west to east, caused by the average temperature of the North Sea water being higher than the temperature in the Kattegat (Fig. A.10). Additionally, we see a cold tendency in areas of large fresh water inflows, e.g. in the Skive-Lovns area towards the south (Fig. A.10). Taking the average measured temperature at each station (Fig. A.10) and comparing with the simulated temperature at the same time and space, the mean bias (modeled - observed) is -0.121 °C. The simulated SST is thus very close to the observed, but slightly too cold. The difference between observations and model are largely brought on by the model failing to reproduce sudden strong spikes in the SST, as illustrated in Fig. A.12. The Pearson correlation coefficient for the spatial domain equals 0.997. Overall, this shows that the model does a good job in simulating the spatial distribution of SST.

Fig. A.11. Modeled versus observed SST at the 15 stations in the Limfjord, each marked by a specific color. The numbering of the stations corresponds to the numbers in Fig. A.10, which shows the location of each station.

The seasonal variation in SST is relatively large, spanning from approximately 0 °C during winter to 20 °C during summer (Figs. A.11 and A.12).

The seasonal cycle of four of the stations have been plotted in Fig. A.12, illustrating that the model largely captures this cycle, though we see a slight tendency towards a delay in summer warming and winter cooling.

The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) between the observed and modeled values is consistently above 0.9 for all years and stations (Table A.2). Notably, the Hals station, at the eastern boundary of the fjord has the lowest correlation with observations, indicating that FlexSem's boundary conditions are not optimal at this location. While the average SST bias generally is low for all stations, the Lovns station shows the largest bias (Table A.2). The Lovns station is heavily affected by run-off from land, indicating that the temperature of the fresh water input to the fjord is slightly too low. This is further confirmed by the fact that stations located in freshwater influenced areas consistently show a negative bias (Station 7, 9 and 12, Table A.2), while the sign of the bias varies between years at the remainder of the stations (Table A.3).

Statistics for the full time series of modeled and observed SST from 2009 to 2017 is summarized in a Taylor diagram (Fig. A.13), confirming a good fit between model and data, with all values having a normalized standard deviation close to one, all correlations being higher than 0.95, and a small mean bias.

Fig. A.12. Modeled and observed seasonal cycle of sea surface temperature at station 1, 4, 6 and 10. See location in Fig. A.10.

Table A.2

Pearson correlation coefficient between sea surface temperature time series from ODA and FlexSem at selected stations. See Fig. A.10 for the location of stations.

Year	St. 1	St. 3	St. 5	St. 7	St. 9	St. 12	St. 15
2009	0.997	0.994	0.996	0.985	0.991	0.997	0.996
2010	0.998	0.989	0.998	0.979	0.995	0.995	0.976
2011	0.996	0.994	0.998	0.964	0.975	0.962	0.959
2012	0.994	0.990	0.997	0.980	0.980	0.996	0.986
2013	0.987	0.997	0.990	0.989	0.955	0.983	0.955
2014	0.990	0.988	0.994	0.987	0.928	0.990	0.954
2015	0.992	0.987	0.998	0.986	0.983	0.997	0.957
2016	0.991	0.983	0.997	0.971	0.958	0.993	0.987
2017	0.989	0.970	0.995	0.981	0.875	0.924	0.994
Mean R	0.993	0.988	0.996	0.980	0.971	0.982	0.974
STD of R	0.004	0.008	0.002	0.008	0.020	0.023	0.017

Table A.3

Bias (ODA minus FlexSem) between sea surface temperature time series from ODA and FlexSem at selected stations. See Fig. A.10 for the location of stations.

Year	St. 1	St. 3	St. 5	St. 7	St. 9	St. 12	St. 15
2009	0.087	-0.192	0.319	-0.388	-0.201	-0.033	0.206
2010	0.222	-0.287	0.115	-0.046	-0.556	-0.306	0.236
2011	0.005	0.037	0.107	-0.150	-0.081	-0.049	0.206
2012	-0.027	-0.329	-0.015	-0.036	-0.438	-0.212	-0.149
2013	0.390	-0.030	-0.146	-0.143	-0.705	-0.348	-0.268
2014	-0.293	-0.595	-0.168	-0.358	-1.149	-0.681	-0.534
2015	-0.082	-0.035	0.078	-0.167	-0.302	-0.181	0.045

(continued on next page)

Table A.3 (continued)

Year	St. 1	St. 3	St. 5	St. 7	St. 9	St. 12	St. 15
2016	-0.157	-0.030	-0.039	-0.579	-0.897	-0.376	-0.122
2017	0.029	0.049	0.076	0.369	-0.481	-0.295	0.145
Mean bias	0.019	-0.157	0.036	-0.166	-0.534	-0.276	-0.026
STD of bias	0.190	0.202	0.141	0.253	0.320	0.184	0.248

Fig. A.13. Taylor diagram showing the correlation, normalized standard deviation, centered root mean square deviation and bias between observed and modeled SST. Cluster A entails stations 1, 2, 3, 5, 10, 11, 14 and 15, B is equal to station 6, cluster C entails stations 4, 7, 8 and 9, cluster D entails stations 12 and 13. Station numbers are marked in Fig. A.10. The time series cover the years 2009 to 2017.

A.2. Salinity

Fig. A.14. Modeled mean sea surface salinity. The black dots mark the location of the CTD stations used to validate the model output along with station numbers: 1) Nissum Broad, 2) Kå s Broad, 3) Sallingsund, 4) Løgstør Broad West, 5) Løgstør Broad East, 6) Nibe Broad, 7) Hals, 8) Bjørnsholm Bay, 9) Riisgård Broad 10) Hvalpsund, 11) Skive, 12) Lovns, 13) Visby Broad, 14) Vilsund, 15) Thisted Broad.

The modeled surface salinity shows a decreasing gradient from west to east (Fig. A.14), brought on by the salinity difference between the high saline water of the North Sea and the brackish water of the Baltic. The freshest water of the Limfjord is found in the Skive-Lovns area (station 11 and 12 in Fig. A.14), which receives 27% ($724 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) of the total runoff to the Limfjord ($2661 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), despite of making up only 10% of the surface area. The spatial Pearson correlation coefficient between the average modeled and observed salinity surface salinity equals 0.840, and the mean bias is -0.188 psu, showing that the model does a reasonable job, though local discrepancies exist as will be shown next.

Fig. A.15. Modeled versus observed surface salinity at the 15 stations in the Limfjord, each marked by a specific color. The numbering of the stations corresponds to the numbers in Fig. A.10, which shows the location of each station.

The spatial salinity gradient across the fjord is also evident when plotting the observed data against model results from the same time and place (Fig. A.15), with the highest salinity at Station 1 by the North Sea and the lowest at station 11 in the Skive-Lovns sub-arm.

Transport of salt into the Limfjord mainly takes place from the small open boundary by the North Sea, from where it is transported along the length of the fjord and into the side arms. The temporal evolution is well captured at Station 1 (Fig. A.16a), and the salt inflow does reach the stations in Løgstør Broad and the sub-arm of Skive Lovns, but the variability is smaller in the model than in observations in 2017 (Fig. A.16). Flexsem's ability to capture the inflow does, however, differ greatly between years, as shown by the variability in the R between modeled and observed salt through the years (Table A.4). An example is station 3, for which R varies between 0.838 in 2013 and 0.083 in 2017. Overall, however, the salinity of the model follows the pattern of the observations fairly well. While the salinity bias is occasionally negative at some stations, FlexSem does show a tendency towards slightly overestimating the salinity in the Limfjord. The largest variability is in the central part of the fjord, while Station 15 by the Kattegat has both a relatively large bias and variability (Table A.5).

Statistics for the full time series of modeled and observed surface salinity from 2009 to 2017 is summarized in a Taylor diagram (Fig. A.17). Here we see a clustering of lower correlations in the Thisted Channel (stations 13 to 15), while the temporal variability is relatively well captured in the remainder of the fjord, with values ranging from 0.5 to 0.8, and with most normalized standard deviations hovering around 1. The variability is mainly brought on by episodic inflow or mixing events, and do not entail a seasonal imprint, making the correlation somewhat smaller than the corresponding values for SST (Fig. A.13).

Fig. A.16. Modeled and observed seasonal cycle of sea surface temperature at station 1, 4, 6 and 10. See location in Fig. A.14.

Table A.4

The Pearson correlation coefficient (R) between sea surface salinity time series from ODA and FlexSem at selected stations. See Fig. A.10 for the location of stations.

Year	St. 1	St. 3	St. 5	St. 7	St. 9	St. 12	St. 15
2009	0.584	0.851	0.909	0.400	0.841	0.702	0.609
2010	0.238	0.469	0.532	0.571	0.556	0.804	0.414
2011	0.752	0.485	0.701	0.437	0.566	0.703	0.711
2012	0.453	0.751	0.510	0.645	0.823	0.288	-0.300
2013	0.776	0.828	0.859	0.834	0.897	0.871	0.966
2014	0.667	0.706	0.451	0.227	0.712	0.608	0.286
2015	0.347	0.793	0.452	0.337	0.362	0.608	0.669
2016	0.613	0.678	0.330	0.255	0.611	0.488	0.935
2017	0.825	0.085	0.599	0.827	0.448	0.629	0.438
Mean of R	0.584	0.627	0.594	0.500	0.646	0.633	0.525
STD of R	0.190	0.231	0.183	0.220	0.174	0.162	0.362

Table A.5

Mean bias between sea surface salinity time series from ODA and FlexSem at selected stations (FlexSem minus ODA values). See Fig. A.10 for the location of stations.

Year	St. 1	St. 3	St. 5	St. 6	St. 9	St. 12	St. 15
2009	0.323	0.819	0.226	-1.184	0.383	0.488	0.009
2010	-0.199	-0.377	0.295	0.571	-0.180	0.123	-0.425
2011	0.262	0.716	0.648	-0.358	0.920	1.665	-0.065
2012	0.692	1.215	0.978	0.361	1.076	0.738	1.311
2013	0.925	1.046	0.162	-0.223	0.231	0.734	0.756
2014	0.941	1.962	1.576	0.545	0.834	0.674	2.285
2015	0.347	1.036	0.977	0.434	1.168	0.910	1.512
2016	1.282	1.460	0.490	0.245	0.873	-0.439	1.794
2017	0.799	0.301	-0.482	0.124	-0.390	-0.177	-0.194
Mean bias	0.597	0.909	0.541	0.057	0.546	0.524	0.776
STD of bias	0.425	0.633	0.559	0.534	0.530	0.591	0.932

Fig. A.17. Taylor diagram showing the correlation, normalized standard deviation, centered root mean square deviation and bias between observed and modeled surface salinity. The annotation numbers mark the stations shown in Fig. A.14. The time series cover the years 2009 to 2017. Notice that station 6 is omitted due to gaps in the observational data.

A.3. Sea surface height

Fig. A.18. Modeled sea surface height. The black dots mark the location of the stations used to validate the model output along with station numbers: A) Thyborøn B) Lemvig C) Struer D) Nykøbing Mors E) Rønbjerg F) Løgstør G) Skive H) Thisted I) Hals.

The SSH is important to evaluate as it gives an indication of the capability of the model to reproduce the currents in the fjord, as well as the SSH. The modeled SSH anomalies are compared to measurement anomalies taken at nine stations in the fjord (Fig. A.18). Due to the approximately six-hour time span of the tidal signal, we are comparing the modeled and observed SSH in 30-minute increments. Periods of gaps in the data are ignored.

Modeled and observed SSH generally shows good agreement (Fig. A.19), with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.935. The variations of SSH are highest towards the North Sea (St. A) and lowest at the Kattegat border (St. I) as the tidal signal is weak by the Kattegat. While the overall fit is good, there is a tendency towards the more extreme measured values of SSH being under-estimated in the model (Fig. A.20). Considering that this is also the case at station A, located right by the western boundary of the fjord, where the SSH is prescribed by boundary conditions, this indicates that these are not variable enough. As the SSH by the North Sea is controlling the inflow to the fjord to a large degree, this is a problem for the SSH at most stations of the fjord.

The temporal evolution of SSH at four stations distributed across the fjord, suggests that in addition to the hardly visible tidal signal, more significant events of low and high SSH occur on a scale of days to weeks. They are driven by atmospheric occurrences, such as wind direction and strength, which control the strength and direction of currents within the fjord. The skill of the model in capturing the variability of SSH is consistent across the years (Table A.6 and Fig. A.21), but again, the lowest correlations between model and observations are found close to the Kattegat boundary.

Fig. A.19. Modeled versus observed SSH at the stations in the Limfjord. The numbering of the stations corresponds to the numbers in Fig. A.18, which shows the location of each station.

Fig. A.20. Modeled and observed seasonal cycle of sea surface temperature at station 1, 4, 6 and 10. See location in Fig. A.14.

Table A.6

Pearson correlation coefficient between measured sea surface height time series and output from FlexSem at selected stations. See Fig. A.18 for the location of stations. Data was not available for the year 2013.

Year	St. B	St. C	St. D	St. F	St. G	St. H	St. I
2009	Lemvig	Struer	Nyk. Mors	Løgstør	Skive	Thisted	Hals
2010	0.938	No data	0.964	0.957	0.948	0.927	0.754
2011	0.927	No data	0.961	0.948	0.958	0.914	0.729
2012	0.958	No data	0.977	0.973	0.971	0.942	0.832
2013	0.919	No data	0.966	0.951	0.954	0.918	0.784
2014	0.933	0.933	0.964	0.955	0.953	0.925	0.774
2015	0.949	0.862	0.971	0.967	0.968	0.940	0.815
2016	0.959	0.911	0.979	0.974	0.968	0.945	0.729

(continued on next page)

Table A.6 (continued)

Year	St. B	St. C	St. D	St. F	St. G	St. H	St. I
2017	0.955	0.937	0.975	0.924	0.967	0.943	0.806
Mean R	0.942	0.911	0.970	0.956	0.961	0.932	0.774
STD of R	0.014	0.030	0.006	0.015	0.008	0.011	0.038

Fig. A.21. Taylor diagram showing the correlation, normalized standard deviation and centered root mean square deviation between measured and modeled sea surface height. The annotation letters mark the stations shown in Fig. A.18. The time series cover the years 2009 to 2017, with the exception of the year 2013 for which we do not have data. Notice that station C is omitted due to gaps in the observational data. As both time series are normalized around their respective mean, the bias is omitted from this plot.

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